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PHE-GLY DIPEPTIDE CARBOXAMIDE SULPHONAMIDES: SYNTHESIS, ELUCIDATION, IN-VITRO AND IN-SILICO ACTIVITIES.

¹Enoo Ojarikre, ²Uchechukwu Christopher Okoro, ³Efeturi Abraham Onoabedje, ⁴Grace Obi, ⁵Vuyisa Mzozoyana, ⁶Mgboh Vivian Onyinye, ⁷Abeokuta Ochuko Johnbull

¹Department of Chemistry,
Faculty of Science, Delta State
University, Abraka, Delta State.
Nigeria...

^{2,3}Department of Pure and Industrial
Chemistry, Faculty of Physical
Sciences, University of Nigeria...

⁴Department of Chemistry,
Federal University of Petroleum
Resources, Effurun, Delta State.
Nigeria...

⁵Department of Chemistry,
School of Chemistry and Physics,
University of KwaZulu-Natal,
South Africa...

⁶Department of Chemistry,
Madonna University, Elele, Rivers
State, Nigeria...

⁷Department of Chemistry,
Southern Delta University, Delta
State, Nigeria...

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Abstract: The combination of sulfonamide, carboxamide, dipeptide and amino groups in a drug candidate is a doorway to compounds with exciting biological activities. The synthesis of three new arylsulphonamoyl Phe-Gly dipeptide carboxamides is reported herein. Three benzenesulphonamide intermediates (**8a-c**) were prepared by reacting benzenesulphonylchloride, 4-nitrobenzenesulphonylchloride, and 4-methylbenzenesulphonylchloride with L-phenylalanine (**7a-c**). The amino protection agent Boc anhydride was used with 1, 4-dioxane to protect the amino group of glycine to form Boc-glycine **2**. The reaction of 4-nitroaniline **3** with Boc-protected glycine yielded Boc-protected carboxamide **4**. The amine deprotection agents DCM/TFA (1:1) were used to produce product **5**. The reaction of the intermediates (**8a-c**) with the deprotected carboxamide produced the Phe-Gly dipeptide target molecules (**9a-c**). The structures were confirmed by FTIR, ¹H-NMR and ¹³C NMR. Computational investigations were performed to ascertain their antibacterial and antifungal potentials. All compounds showed good binding. The binding energies (kcal/mol) for antibacterial and antifungal activities -7.0 to -7.6 and -8.1 to 10.1 respectively. Antimicrobial studies were conducted to ascertain the potencies of the compounds against two Gram positive bacteria (Staphylococcus aureus and Streptococcus pyogene), two Gram negative bacteria (Pseudomonas aeruginosa and Escherichia coli), and Candida albicans. The inhibitory zone diameter (IZD) values were 2-40 mm. The MIC values in (mg/mL) were 1.585 – 7.586 and the MBC values (mg/mL) were 12.500 - 25.500. The compounds showed the highest activities toward Streptococcus pyogene and Escherichia coli. Computational studies were also conducted to determine the binding energies of the proteins in interaction with (1U1Z), (2W9S), (4KT6), (4X08), and (4YDE). The binding energies were in the range -5.6 to -10.1. The predicted hepatotoxicity, carcinogenicity, immunotoxicity, mutagenicity, and cytotoxicity of the compounds also showed that they are good drug candidates.

Keywords: Antibacterial, antifungal, carboxamides, aryl, sulfonamides, dipeptide, docking, in silico and in vivo.

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1.0 Introduction.

Sulfonamides are a very important class of compounds in the pharmaceutical industry. They have proven to be successful as preventive and chemotherapeutic agents against many diseases (Ekoh et al., 2021; Ezugwu et al., 2020; Ekoh et al., 2022). More advanced studies have revealed that modified sulfonamides have high to moderate antibacterial activity (Ochu et al., 2024; Ezugwu et al., 2028). Over the years, research has been conducted on the antimalarial, antitrypanosomal, antidiabetic, and antioxidant potentials of sulfonamides, carboxamides, and dipeptides compounds and remains unabated (Ezugwu et al., 2024). However, very few reports have been published on the antifungal and antibacterial potential of these compounds. In addition, very few studies have been reported on the synthesis of compounds containing dipeptide, sulfonamide, and carboxamide functional groups in one molecule. To date, there are very few reports on arylsulphonamoyl 'Phe-Gly' dipeptide carboxamides exist (Onoabedje et al., 2020). A dipeptide is produced when two amino acids are joined together by a peptide bond. Because the dipeptide consists of two amino acids, it can have a different sequence. For example, Ala-Gly and Gly-Ala. Ala-Gly has chemical and biological properties that are different from those of Gly-Ala. This is because, if the amino acids are joined as in Gly-Ala, the glycine will have a free amino group at the terminal end, while alanine will have a free carboxyl end (Onoabedje et al., 2021). Discussing the reactivity of dipeptides as amino acid derivatives is easy because the amino acids in the dipeptide are degraded in the organism to form the constituent amino acids (Lavanya, 2017; Ochu et al., 2024; Abo and Ashidi, 1999). Therefore, they will retain their physicochemical properties and hence their physiological effects. L-glutamine which is heat labile, is a good example, whereas a dipeptide of L-alanine and L-glutamine is more tolerant to heat (Gui, 2017). This can also be seen in the solubility of some notable dipeptides (Onyejekwe et al., 2024). Tyr is insoluble, but Ala-Tyr dipeptide has a solubility of 14 g/L (Ezugwu et al., 2020). A number of dipeptides are more soluble than each of the constitutive amino acid. For example, the solubility of Ala and Gln are 89 and 36 g/L respectively, but the solubility of the dipeptide Ala-Gln has a solubility of 586 g/L (Tacic et al., 2017). These properties and the fact that Ala-Gln and Gly-Tyr are quickly degraded into individual amino acids when taken into the body, these dipeptides are used as components of patients' infusions (Trott and Olson, 2010; Supuran, 2008)

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Instrumentation

Analytical grade reagents were used in this research and were bought from Sigma-Aldrich and DBH. The reagents were used as delivered without any other purification. Precoated plates were used for thin layer chromatography. Plates were purchased from Onitsa Market, Onitsa, Anambra State, Nigeria. Iodine crystals were used to develop the TLC plates. For the FTIR analysis, an IR M530 Buck Scientific infrared spectrophotometer was used, and potassium bromide was the support material. The MDJ-5S Searchtech instrument was used to determination the melting point of the synthesized compounds. The proton and carbon-13 NMR spectra were determined at the School of Chemistry and Physics, Westville Campus, University of KwaZulu-Natta, Durban 3629, South Africa, using 600 MHz spectrometers in CDCl_3 with tetramethylsilane as the internal standard. The in silico analysis for anti-bacteria and antifungal potentials was also conducted using Auto Dock Vina version 4.2 by PyRx, a graphical user interface program. The in vitro antibacterial and antifungal activities against *S. aureus*, *S. pyogenes*, *P. aeruginosa*, *E. coli* and *C. albican* were determined using standard methods. In the antimicrobial study, two gram-positive organisms (*S. aureus* ATCC 9027 and; *S. pyogenes*), two Gram-negative organisms (*Escherichia coli* ATCC 6538P and; *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*), and a yeast fungus (*Candida albican*) were studied.

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All microorganisms used in this research were obtained from the microbial bank of the Department of Pharmaceutical Microbiology, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Agbani. They were maintained on Mueller-Hinton Agar medium.

2.2 General procedure for synthesizing substituted

2-(benzenesulphonamido)-3-benzenepropanoic acid (8a-c).

To a cleaned and dried two necked flask was added distilled water (15 mL), sodiumtrioxocarbonate (IV) (1.5g, 14.2mmol), L-phenylalanine (2g, 12.12 mmol) and the solution was continuously stirred with a magnetic stirrer until all the solute dissolved finely. Crushed ice was used to cool the reaction mixture to 2°C and appropriate benzenesulphonylchloride (12.12 mmol) (2a-c) was added in four portions over a period of 1 h. This was followed by continuous stirring at room temperature for 4 h. The purity of the products was ascertained using precoated TLC plates (acetone/ n-hexane 1:9). The mixture was then acidified with 20% aqueous hydrochloric acid HCl to pH 2 were products (3a-c) obtained in analytical grade after washing with tartaric acid solution of pH 2.2. The product was dried over fused silica gel in a dessicator.

2.3 General procedure glycine protection with di-ter-butylidicarbonate (Boc anhydride) (2).

Glycine 4 was dissolved in water (20 mL) and sodium bicarbonate NaHCO₃ (2g, 23.8 mmol) was added, and the solution was continuously stirred using a magnetic stirrer. Then, it was cooled to 5°C and Boc anhydride (1.5g, 6.87 mmol) was slowly added as a solution in 1, 4-dioxane (10mL). The solution was then stirred at 0°C for 1 h and allowed to warm to room temperature overnight. Then, water was then added, and the aqueous layer was extracted 2 times with ethylacetate (EtOAc). The organic layer was back extracted twice with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution. The combined aqueous layers were acidified to pH 1 with 10% HCl, then extracted 3 times with (EtOAc). The combined organic layers were dried to obtain the product 2-((tert-butoxycarbonyl) amino)ethanoic acid 5.

2.4 General procedure for the synthesizing the carboxamide derivatives of

2-((tert-butoxycarbonyl) amino) ethanoic acid (4)

To a mixture of para-nitroaniline (2.98 45.15 mmole) (3), 1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl) carboxamide (EDC) (1g, 5.22 mmole), 1M HCl (5.0 mL) and anhydrous 1-hydroxybenzotriazole (HOBt) (1.2g, 8.88 mmole) in a two necked flask was added DCM (5.0 mL) and N, N-diisopropylethylamine (DIPEA) (5.0 mL) and the reaction mixture was stirred for 30 min at 27°C. Then, boc-glycine (1mL) (2) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred for 12 hours. Thereafter, crushed ice was added to the product in a beaker and left to cool. Then, the beaker was filtered, and the residue was air dried overnight to obtain the product (4). The purity of the glycine-boc carboxamides was ascertained using precoated TLC plates (acetone: n-hexane 30:70) and was found to be pure.

2.5 General standard deprotection procedure for amines (5).

Compound 4 was dissolved in 10 mL of 1:1 trifluoroacetic acid, DCM 10mL and stirred at room temperature for 2 h. The purity of the product 5 was confirmed using precoated TLC plates (30:70, acetone:nhexane) and was found to be pure.

2.6 General procedure for the synthesizing of Phe-Gly Dipeptide carboxamide sulfonamide.

Benzenesulphonamides (8a-c) (5.747 mmole), EDC (10mL), 1M HCl (5.0 mL) and HOBt (10.0 mL) in a necked flask was added DCM (5.0 mL) and DIPEA (5.0mL) and the reaction mixture was stirred for 30 minutes at room temperature. Then, the carboxamide derivative (5) (5.747 mmole) was added and the reaction was stirred for 18

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hours. Thereafter, crushed ice was added to the product in a beaker and left to cool. Then the beaker contents were filtered and the residue was air dried overnight to obtain the product (**9a-c**). The purity of the product was tested using precoated TLC plates (acetone:n-hexane 30:70) and was found to be pure.

3.4.1 2-(4-methylphenylsulphonamido)-N-(2-((4-nitrophenyl) amino)-2-oxoethyl)-3-phenylpropanamide (**9a**).

9a

Light-brown crystals. **Yield;** (3.410g, 67%). **Melting point** 297°C. (**FTIR (KBr, cm⁻¹)** 3323 (NH), 3081 (C-H stretch of aromatic), 2714 (amino acid), 1624 (C=O), 1442 (NO₂), 1329 (2S=O). ¹H NMR: δ8.03 (1H, s, CONH proton), δ8.03 (1H, s, CONH proton), δ8.60 (2H, d, J-7.61 Hz, Ar-H), 8.40, (2H, d, J = 7.45, Ar-H), 8.39, 7.39, 7.27 (5H, m, Ar-H), 7.29, 7.26 (4H, m, Ar-H), δ7.21 (1H, dd, J = 9.15, 8.60Hz, SO₂NH). δ3.91 (2H, s, CH₂), δ3.89 (2H, d, J = 7.45, CH₂) 2.75 (1H, t, CH), 2.34 (3H,s, CH₃). **δ_C (600MHz, DMSO):** In the ¹³C NMR: 171.21, 167.40 (C=O), δ 161.40, 149.68, 146.64, 139.15, 130.24, 128.12, 127.12, 126.07, 126.2, 125.90, 124.00, 122.10 (12C, Ar-C), 51.20 (1C, CH), δ40.00 and 35.87 (CH₂), δ22.30 (CH₃ group).

3.5.2 N-(2-((4-nitrophenyl) amino)-2-oxoethyl)-2-(4-nitrophenylsulphonamido)-3-phenylpropanamide (**9b**).

9b

Milk colored crystals. **Yield** (4.017g, 74%). **Melting point** 130^o– 130.5^o C. (**FTIR (KBr, cm⁻¹)** 3286 (amino acid), 2904 (C-H aliphatic), 1639 (C=O), 1449 (NO₂), 1254 (SO₂N), 842 (NH deformation). ¹H NMR: δ8.90 (1H, s, CONH proton), δ7.60 (1H, s, CONH proton), δ8.40 (2H, d, J = 8.00Hz,Ar-H), 8.30 (2H, d, J = 7.50 Hz, Ar-H), 8.24 (2H, d, J = 7.00 Hz, Ar-H), 8.10, (2H, d, J = 7.45Hz, Ar-H), 7.72, 7.21, 7.10 (5H, m, Ar-H), δ7.32 (1H, s, SO₂NH proton), δ3.97 (1H, t, methine proton), δ4.90 and 3.29 (2H, m, methylene proton), 4.14 (2H, s, CH₂). **δ_C (600MHz, DMSO):** ¹³C NMR: 170.11 (C=O), 169.40 (C=O), δ 168.10, 150.10, 143.5, 141.20, 140.00, 139.15, 128.20, 127.60, 126.20, 125.00, 123.00, 121.10 (12C, Ar-C), 59.20 (methine carbon), δ41.50 and 36.70 (CH₂).

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3.5.3 N-(2-((4-nitrophenyl) amino)-2-oxoethyl)-3-phenyl-2-(phenylsulphonamido)propanamide (9c).

9c

Appearance: brown-crystals. **Yield** (4.246g, 86%). **Melting point** 302°- 302.5°C. **FTIR (KBr, cm⁻¹)** 3461 (secondary amide), 3202 (C-H stretch of aromatic), 2637, 2730. (Amino acid), 1631 (C=O), 1440 (NO₂), 1347 (2S=O). **δ_H:(600MHz, DMSO):** ¹H NMR: : δ8.50 (1H, s, CONH proton), δ8.06 (1H, s, CONH proton), δ8.24 (2H, d, J = 7.2Hz, Ar-H), 7.96 (2H, d, J = 7.00Hz, Ar-H), 8.24, 7.80, 7.71 (5H, m, Ar-H), 7.60, 7.42, 7.00 (5H, m, Ar-H), δ7.52 (1H, s, SO₂NH proton), δ4.02 (1H, t, methine proton), δ3.30 and 3.29 (2H, m, methylene proton), 4.14 (2H, s, CH₂). **δ_c (600MHz, DMSO):** ¹³C NMR: 170.11 (C=O), 169.40 (C=O), δ 168.10, 150.10, 143.5, 141.20, 140.00, 139.15, 128.20, 127.60, 126.20, 125.00, 123.00, 121.10 (12C, Ar-C), 40.02 (methine carbon), δ39.86 and 39.58 (CH₂).

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

3.1 Chemistry of reaction.

3.1.1 Spectra characterization

Scheme 1: Glycine protection with Boc.

Scheme 2: Boc-glycine reaction with 4-nitroaniline.

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Scheme 3: Deprotection of the carboxamide.

Scheme 4: Synthesis of benzenesulphonamides derivatives.

Scheme 5: Synthesis of Phe-Gly dipeptide carboxamides.

Table 1: Inhibition zone diameter of compound 9a.

Concentration (mg/mL)	P. aeruginosa (mm)	S. aureus (mm)	S. pyogene (mm)	E. coli (mm)	C. albican (mm)
25.000	18	12	-	25	18
12.500	16	10	-	14	14
6.250	4	8	10	11	12
3.125	-	6	2	8	8
1.562	-	-	-	5	-
Streptomycin					Fluconazole
Concentration (mg/mL)	P.	S. aureus (mm)	S. pyogene (mm)	E. coli (mm)	C. albican (mm)

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	aeruginosa (mm)				
10.000	-	-	-	-	36
5.000	36	36	40	40	32
2.500	25	25	32	32	23
1.250	19	19	23	23	16
0.625	13	13	16	16	12
0.313	8	8	12	12	-

As shown in **Table 1**, the sensitivity of Escherichia coli is the highest in both gram-positive, gram-negative and fungus groups. At 1.562 mg/mL the other organisms did not show sensitivity for the compound but E. coli had an IZD of 5 mm. The organisms showed better sensitivities to the standard drug in both bacteria and fungi.

Table 2: Inhibition zone diameter of compound **9b**.

Concentration (mg/mL)	P. aeruginosa (mm)	S. aureus (mm)	S. pyogene (mm)	E. coli (mm)	C. albican (mm)
25.000	-	12	-	-	8
12.500	-	6	-	-	4
6.250	-	4	-	-	2
3.125	-	-	-	-	-
1.562	-	-	-	-	-
Streptomycin					Fluconazole
Concentration (mg/mL)	P. aeruginosa (mm)	S. aureus (mm)	S. pyogene (mm)	E. coli (mm)	C. albican (mm)
10.000	-	-	-	-	36
5.000	36	36	40	40	32
2.500	25	25	32	32	23
1.250	19	19	23	23	16
0.625	13	13	16	16	12
0.313	8	8	12	12	-

P. aeruginosa, S. pyogene, and E. coli were not show susceptibility to compound **9b**. The highest sensitivity was shown by S. aureus and C. albican.

Table 3: Inhibition zone diameter of compound **9c**.

Concentration (mg/mL)	P. aeruginosa (mm)	S. aureus (mm)	S. pyogene (mm)	E. coli (mm)	C. albican (mm)
25.000	10	12	11	8	13
12.500	8	6	6	5	10

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6.250	4	2	4	4	8
3.125	-	-	-	-	4
1.562	-	-	-	-	-
Streptomycin					Fluconazole
Concentration (mg/mL)	P. aeruginosa (mm)	S. aureus (mm)	S. pyogene (mm)	E. coli (mm)	C. albican (mm)
10.000	-	-	-	-	36
5.000	36	36	40	40	32
2.500	25	25	32	32	23
1.250	19	19	23	23	16
0.625	13	13	16	16	12
0.313	8	8	12	12	-

Table 3 shows that *C. albican* has the highest sensitivity for compound **9c**. At a concentration of 10 mg/mL, both the gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria do not show sensitivity to the standard drug, only the fungus does.

Table 4: Minimum Inhibitory Concentration of Compounds **9a**, **9b** and **9c**.

Compound	P. aeruginosa (mg/mL)	S. aureus (mg/mL)	S. pyogene (mg/mL)	E. coli (mg/mL)	C. albican (mg/mL)
9a	-	5.012	2.754	-	1.585
9b	1.738	7.586	2.455	-	2.455
9c	-	-	2.089	7.244	6.166

The minimum inhibitory concentration is the lowest concentration of the drug that prevents the growth of microorganism. Table 4 shows that the best MIC is **9c** towards *S. pyogenes*. **9a**, **9b**, and **9c** showed good MIC for *S. pyogene*.

Table 5: Minimum bactericidal concentration of compounds **9a**, **9b** and **9c**.

Compound	P. aeruginosa (mg/mL)	S. aureus (mg/mL)	S. pyogene (mg/mL)	E. coli (mg/mL)	C. albican (mg/mL)
9a	-	12.500	25.000	-	25.000
9b	25.00	25.000	12.500	-	12.500
9c	-	-	25.000	25.000	12.500
Streptomycin	0.479	0.479	0.479	0.447	-
Fluconazole	-	-	-	-	0.699

Among the organisms, *S. pyogene* and *C. albicans* showed similar MBC for the compounds. All organisms showed good MBC for the 9a, 9b and 9c. The MBCs of the compounds studied are comparable to those of the standard drugs.

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Table 6: Druglikeness and bioavailability of compounds **9a**, **9b** and **9c**.

Property	9a	9b	9c
Molecular weight (g/mol)	498.55	531.54	484.53
Hydrogen bond donor (Hbd)	3	3	3
Hydrogen bond acceptor	7	9	7
Log P	4.16	3.44	3.85
Bioavailability	0.55	0.17	0.55
Log S	-4.16	-3.50	-3.86
Topological polar surface area (\AA^2)	115.99	119.23	115.99

From the Lipinski rule of five (Table 6).

Molecular weight is $\leq 500 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$, **hydrogen bond donor** is ≤ 5 , **hydrogen bond acceptor** is ≤ 10 , **Log P** must be ≤ 5 , **bioavailability** is between 0 and 1, and **Log S** is in a range: -2 to 0 is extremely soluble, -4 to -2 is moderately soluble and less than -4 is insoluble. The **TPSA** must be within the range of 0 to $140(\text{\AA}^2)$. TPSA has a positive correlation with mass, and the molecules with masses higher than 5.00 g/mol are known to have TPSA values beyond the range of 0 to $140(\text{\AA}^2)$ and are not safe for consumption (Ezugwu et al., 2020).

Table 7: Binding energy and inhibition constant for compounds 9a, 9b, and 9c and xanthine oxidase (1fiq).

Compound	Binding Energy (Kcal/mol)	Inhibition Constant (μm)
9a	-10.4	0.023
9b	-10.1	0.039
9c	-10.3	0.028
Allopurinol	-5.8	55.443

As shown in **Table 7**, the smaller the free energy of binding, the smaller the inhibition constant. The lower the B.E, the better it fits into the pockets of the protein and the better the interaction with the amino acids of the proteins (Ekoh et al., 2022; Ekoh et al., 2021). All these compounds exhibited better binding energies and inhibition constants than the standard drug.

Table 8: Predicted hepatotoxicity, carcinogenicity, immunotoxicity, mutagenicity and cytotoxicity of compounds 9a, 9b, and 9c.

Property	9a	9b	9c
LD ₅₀ (mg/kg)	1000	5000	5000
Toxicity class	5	6	6
Hepatotoxicity	0.59	0.61	0.61
Carcinogenicity	0.62	0.61	0.61
Immunogenicity	0.99	0.99	0.99
Mutagenicity	0.52	0.53	0.53
Cytotoxicity	0.64	0.62	0.62

Toxicity classes are defined using the internationally agreed upon technique of chemical labelling for LD₅₀. The toxicity classes are:

Class 1: Fatal if swallowed ($\text{LD}_{50} \leq 5$)

Class 2: Fatal if swallowed ($5 < \text{LD}_{50} \leq 50$)

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Class 3: Toxic if swallowed ($50 < LD_{50} \leq 300$)

Class 4: Harmful if swallowed ($300 < LD_{50} \leq 2000$)

Class 5: May be harmful if swallowed ($2000 < LD_{50} \leq 5000$)

Class 6: Nontoxic ($LD_{50} > 5000$)

Table 8 shows that compound 9b and 9c are non-toxic.

Table 9: B.E of the ligand and Proteins (1U1Z), (2W9S), (4KT6), (4X08), and (4YDE).

Compound	(1U1Z)	(2W9S)	(4KT6)	(4X08)	(4YDE)
9a	-6.6	-8.0	-8.5	-5.9	-7.7
9b	-7.1	-10.1	-7.9	-6.4	-8.7
9c	-5.9	-9.1	-7.8	-5.7	-7.3
Streptomycin	-5.9	-7.4	-9.0	-5.8	-6.5
Fluconazole	-6.6	-7.3	-7.1	-5.6	-6.0

Pseudomonas aeruginosa (1U1Z), *Staphylococcus aureus* (2W9S), *Streptococcus pyogenes* (4KT6), and *Candida albican* (4X08) were used.

The lower the binding energy, the better the binding to the target protein molecule. As shown in Table 9, all the studied compounds showed binding energies that are comparable to the binding energies of the standard drugs.

4.0 CONCLUSION

The synthesis of three novel sulfonamoyl 'phe-gly' dipeptide carboxamide derivatives and their in silico and in vitro properties was achieved using versatile method. The novel compounds were characterized using FTIR, ^1H NMR, and ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy, and the spectra were consistent with the assigned structures. Regarding the structure of the structure of 2WPS, all the compounds showed good binding energies than streptomycin. 9a, 9b, and 9c showed good binding for all protein structures. The growing report of antimicrobial resistance needs concerted effort in the discovery of new potent antimicrobial agents. The molecular docking results showed good binding affinity with the active site of the protein affinity using conventional hydrogen bonding.

4.1 Ethics Approval and Consent To the Participate

Not applicable.

4.2 Human and Animal Rights

Not applicable as no human or animal was used in this experiment.

4.3 Consent for Publication

Not applicable.

4.4 Availability of Data and Materials

All data and materials supporting the findings of the study are available within the manuscripts and its supplementary files.

4.5 Funding

There is no funding.

4.6 Conflict of Interest

There is none.

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